

The Coupling Constants Series and QFT Commuter - 8T

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial equation of coupling constants magnitudes of the new 8T, alongside of the main equation, and in particular the arbitrary variation term to vanish into matter, it is possible to intersect with the idea of the QFT commutation anti-commutation relation. Fermions anti-commute because the arbitrary variation term must vanish, and bosons commute because they are net variation on the manifold.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

Up until now, reader is probably familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. From here on out, we have a completely new paper. In QFT one of the most important ideas which emphasize the difference between fermions to bosons is the mathematical expression commuting/anti commuting relations for bosons and fermions respectively. The term is presented in the following form:

$$[A_i, B_i]_{\pm} = 0$$

Fermions anti commute, summed as zero when combined and bosons commute, the only they to be summed as zero as if they are subtracted from one another. The actual way of QFT representation is not important in this paper. The idea of the commuting anti-commuting relations of bosons and fermions is in perfect agreement with the 8T. As was presented in the thesis, the arbitrary variations term is associated with fermions. We require the term to vanish, so when partitioned we needed an even amount of two distinct elements which differ in sign.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

On the other hand, the bosons were regarded as net curvature of discrete prime amounts as described by the primorial, which add up to a positive summation, so they only way to eliminate them is to subtract from one another. That is in agreement with QFT idea of commutation relation. The term describing Bosons is (1.49):

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

Overall, one of the most important ideas in Quantum Field Theory is in perfect intersection with the 8T. We can visualize it and reason why that is from an angle of curvature on the matrix tensor using the main equation and primorial. We can even use the commutator on the two terms.

$$[\delta g_i \delta g'_i]_{\pm} = 0 \quad (1.5)$$

The first term in the commuting relation (1.5) is describing the partitioned terms, the second is the acceleration. Fermions will accelerate toward each other, in agreement with vanishing curvature. Bosons will accelerate to a joint point on the matrix tensor. That is because each bosons is a net curvature that increase the probability of arrival to itself. As was analyzed before, 8T and QFT does not contradict one another.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)